

Comparison of Novel Classical and Developed AI Techniques for SAR Oil Spill Detection

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Abstract—Oil spills (OS) are hazards to marine ecosystems, necessitating timely and accurate monitoring. Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) offers a robust remote sensing capability for detecting OS across wide areas under all-weather conditions. This study employs dual-pol SAR with VV and VH channels to propose a novel combination of polarimetric descriptors (PDs) for efficient OS detection and classification. Furthermore, the ensemble learning Random Forest (RF) algorithm developed in the AI-OBSERVER project provides reliable and accurate OS detection. The qualitative analysis of PDs highlights their effectiveness, while the $\mathcal{H} (1 - \mathcal{A})$ descriptor demonstrates strong potential for OS classification. Comparative analysis of the proposed PD and RF demonstrates high accuracy in detecting central OS regions, and the experimental results further validate the balanced performance of the PD and RF-based OS detection model. This work aims to detect OS in Cyprus for monitoring and to prevent illegal dumping.

Index Terms—Oil spill detection, Synthetic aperture radar, random forest classifier, polarimetric descriptor

I. INTRODUCTION

Marine oil pollution causes significant challenges to offshore activities, tourism, marine habitats, and ecosystems. Numerous incidents of oil spills (OS), both accidental and intentional, have been reported in the past, leading to severe and long-lasting damages to marine ecosystems and coastal activities [1]–[3].

Although optical sensors in remote sensing provide abundant information for marine environment monitoring, their effectiveness is limited by weather conditions and reliance on solar radiance, making them unsuitable for OS detection at night or during adverse clouds

[4], [5]. The spread of OS must be timely and accurately monitored, which is important for ensuring marine safety and environmental security. Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) is widely utilized for remotely detecting OS due to its capability to operate effectively under nearly all weather conditions, both day and night [6]–[9]. The polarimetric scattering characteristics of OS observed with dual-pol SAR have advanced significantly as SAR technology evolved from single-polarization to polarimetric imaging.

In dual-Pol SAR, electromagnetic waves are transmitted and received in VV and VH polarizations, generating a scattering matrix that captures the target’s physical properties. Oil slicks, by smoothing the marine surface, reduce Bragg scattering, creating dark regions in PolSAR images. These dark spots are effectively detected using polarimetric descriptors (PDs), allowing for the identification of oil slicks on the sea surface [10], [11].

For active SAR systems, where the radar cross section (RCS) of OS and seawater is often indistinguishable, traditional thresholding techniques fail to differentiate between OS and water, rendering visual interpretation insufficient. Natural phenomena like low wind speeds and heavy rainfall can create “look-alikes” in SAR images, appearing as dark regions with low backscattering, similar to OS. To address these limitations, polarimetric descriptors (PDs), including entropy (\mathcal{H}), alpha (α), and anisotropy (\mathcal{A}), provide an effective means of discrimination [12], [13]. The \mathcal{H}/α decomposition algorithm leverages these parameters to quantify scattering characteristics within a specific zone, enabling the classification of OS types.

In this paper, we investigated polarimetric features and analyzed a novel combination $\mathcal{H} (1 - \mathcal{A})$ that provides accurate detection and classification of OS (thick oil, thin oil, and sea water). To verify OS detection, two SAR scenes are selected around Cyprus, and the results

of central OS are compared with well-established random forest (RF) deployed in the AI-OBSERVER (<https://ai-observer.eu>). RF effectively manages large, high-dimensional datasets, handles missing values, and resists overfitting, ensuring robustness even with noisy data. Its ability to capture complex non-linear relationships makes it ideal for applications like OS detection [14]. This tool is assisting the ERATOTHENES to reach its long-term objective of raising excellence on AI for EO on environmental hazards [15].

II. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

In this study, we utilized single-look complex (SLC) dual-polarization data from Sentinel-1, leveraging its global monitoring capabilities and responsiveness in emergencies, which are essential for scientific research.

A. Data pre-processing in SNAP Toolbox

Initially, the second sub-swath of the three available sub-swaths was extracted using the `S-1 TOPS Split` tool. The satellite orbit file information was then updated with the `Apply Orbit File` tool. Following this, preprocessing steps included complex calibration, demodulation, and data debursting. Complex calibration was performed using the `Calibration` tool to relate pixel values to the actual radar backscatter. Demodulation and debursting were executed using the `S-1 TOPS DerampDmod` and `Deburst` tools, which merged all bursts within the selected sub-swath and resampled the data to a common pixel spacing grid in both range and azimuth directions. Finally, a `Land-Sea Mask` was applied to exclude land areas, simplifying subsequent processing steps [16].

B. Polarimetric Descriptors (PDs)

In a dual-pol SAR system, the backscattered signal, comprising both amplitude and phase information, is represented by a complex scattering matrix \mathbf{S} , defined as [17]:

$$\mathbf{S} = [S_{VV} \quad S_{VH}]^T \quad (1)$$

The polarimetric covariance matrix (PCM) is given as:

$$\mathbf{C} = \langle \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{S}^{*T} \rangle = \begin{bmatrix} \langle |S_{VV}|^2 \rangle & \langle S_{VV} S_{VH}^* \rangle \\ \langle S_{VH} S_{VV}^* \rangle & \langle |S_{VH}|^2 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where T denotes the transpose operator and $*$ represents the complex conjugate operator.

The PCM can be expressed as a weighted sum of orthogonal matrices. Let \mathbf{U} be a unitary matrix that facilitates eigen-decomposition, defined as:

$$\mathbf{U} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}^\dagger = \sum_{q=1}^2 \lambda_q \mathbf{u}_q \mathbf{u}_q^\dagger \quad (3)$$

where \dagger represents the Hermitian operator (complex conjugate transpose), such that $\mathbf{U}^\dagger = \mathbf{U}^{*T}$. The matrix \mathbf{U}

contains the eigenvectors \mathbf{u}_q , where q is rank of matrix, while λ_1 and λ_2 ($\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2$) are the eigenvalues of the coherency matrix. Once the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the PCM are computed, key scattering characteristics can be derived. The eigenvalues λ_1 and λ_2 are used to define entropy (\mathcal{H}), which quantifies the randomness in the scattering process:

$$\mathcal{H} = - \sum_{q=1}^2 p_q \log_2(p_q), \quad \mathcal{H} \in [0, 1] \quad (4)$$

where $p_q = \frac{\lambda_q}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2}$. The anisotropy (\mathcal{A}), complementing entropy, describes the relative difference between the two eigenvalues and is defined as:

$$\mathcal{A} = \frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2}, \quad \mathcal{A} \in [0, 1]. \quad (5)$$

The mean angle alpha (α) represents the dominant scattering mechanisms and is defined as:

$$\alpha = \sum_{q=1}^2 p_q \cos^{-1}(|\mathbf{u}_q(1)|), \quad \alpha \in [0, 90^\circ] \quad (6)$$

The value of α varies to indicate scattering types: surface scattering occurs near 0° , volume scattering around 45° , and double-bounce scattering near 90° .

C. PDs ($\mathcal{H}/\mathcal{A}/\alpha$) Decomposition

PDs are effective tools for analyzing physical scattering mechanisms, especially for OS detection. Using \mathcal{H} - α decomposition as proposed by Lee and Pottier [18], the scattering samples are distributed in specific subzones on the \mathcal{H} - α plane, where each subzone corresponds to distinct scattering behaviors and target types.

- For OS regions: α is generally intermediate, \mathcal{H} is significantly higher compared to seawater or look-alike regions. For seawater: α is relatively low, \mathcal{H} is comparatively high for OS. This decomposition provides a clear distinction OS.
- Upon experiments with PDs to study the scattering characteristics, we found that the PDs combination $\mathcal{H} (1 - \mathcal{A})$ provides accurate detection and classification of OS. In the next section, we analyze these results to extract meaningful insights.

D. Random Forest (RF) Algorithm

The comparison leverages the RF algorithm to classify Sentinel-1 data for OS detection. The first step involved defining the area of interest using precise geometric coordinates. The data were then filtered for the dates of August 29 and 30, 2021, utilizing VV polarization images in IW mode. A speckle filter with a 100-meter window was applied to reduce image noise and enhance clarity. Threshold masks set at -27dB were used to isolate relevant areas for further analysis. Training data

TABLE I: Basic information of the sensor’s source.

Imaging Parameter	Details
Polarimetric States	VV and VH
Product Type	Single Look Complex (SLC)
Band	C (5.045) GHz
Mode	Interferometric Wide Swath
Swath	250 km
Spatial Resolution	5 m × 20 m
Incidence Angle	33.86° – 42.93°

Fig. 1: Excerpt of SAR scene amplitude images, (a) acquired on 29-08-2021 and (b) acquired on 30-08-2021; (c) and (d) are Pauli RGB images of OS areas defined as $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [|S_{VV} - S_{VH}|, |S_{VV} + S_{VH}|, |S_{VH}|^2]$.

for both oil spills and water bodies were collected to train the Random Forest classifier, which was set to use 50 decision trees. Classification was conducted for both dates, categorizing the data into two categories: water and oil spills. This methodology ensures high accuracy and efficiency in detecting oil spills, demonstrating the versatility and reliability of Random Forest in remote sensing applications [19].

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We analyzed two SLC SAR scenes over the Mediterranean Sea near Cyprus. Figure 1 presents excerpts from Sentinel-1 OS amplitude images: (a) acquired on 29 – 08 – 2021, and (b) acquired on 30 – 08 – 2021. The Pauli color-coded images of the dataset used are shown in (c) and (d). The polarimetric information of the scattering matrix is represented by the combination of the intensities in a single RGB image. However, lookalike regions in Pauli images appear as darker as the thick OS. The basic information about the sensor is given in Table 1. The preprocessing pipeline is detailed in the previous section. Dark patches in the images correspond to OS; however, under calm sea conditions, both OS and seawater appear similarly dark. To enhance detection and improve the classification of OS, we applied PDs.

Figure 2 shows the qualitative results of key PD parameters for distinguishing OS from seawater and lookalike regions. The entropy (\mathcal{H}) is notably higher for OS, moderate for lookalikes or mixed oil-water, and lower for seawater, reflecting variations in randomness. Anisotropy (\mathcal{A}) is lower for OS, intermediate for lookalikes, and

significantly higher for seawater, indicating distinct scattering properties. The alpha (α) representing the mean scattering angle is relatively high for OS and lower for seawater, revealing differences in dominant scattering mechanisms. The proposed $\mathcal{H} (1 - \mathcal{A})$ PD further enhances OS detection, showing higher values for OS and lower values for seawater, with lookalikes exhibiting less distinct characteristics. These results demonstrate a clear visual distinction between OS and seawater, supporting the efficacy of the extracted novel combination of PDs in identifying and classifying OS.

Figure 3 presents the traditional \mathcal{H} - α classification, where (a) shows the classification plane divided into nine zones (Z1, Z2,... Z9), each corresponding to distinct physical scattering information. The analysis reveals that for both SAR scenes, the scattering primarily appears within zones Z9, Z6, and Z3, as shown in (b) and (c), indicating the presence of low, medium, and high entropy surface scattering, respectively. Whereas $\log_{10}^{(n)}$ is the density of pixels in those zones. Specifically, scatterings

Fig. 2: Visualization of PDs: (a) Entropy, (b) Anisotropy, (c) Alpha, and (d) proposed PD.

Fig. 3: PD decomposition proposed by Lee and Poirter (a) \mathcal{H} - α plane, (b) \mathcal{H} - α decomposition for SAR acquired on 29-08-2021, and (c) for SAR acquired on 30-08-2021.

Fig. 4: Quantitative comparison of thick OS (red), thin or lookalike OS (green), and water (blue) for both data classified by (a) \mathcal{H} , (b) \mathcal{A} , and (c) $\mathcal{H}(1 - \mathcal{A})$.

in Z9 are associated with water; Z6 represents lookalike or thin oil layers; and Z3 is characteristic of thick OS. This $\mathcal{H}-\alpha$ provides valuable observations of the target’s nature and their underlying physical information.

It can be observed from Figure 4 that the proposed PD classifies thick OS and water class correctly with minimum error for lookalike classes as compared to other PDs. The accuracy ranges from 92.5% to 96.5% which is significant as compared to manual interpretation of OS and classification. Figure 5 is the detection and classification of OS for both methodologies. (a) and (b) are the classifications of thick OS, thin OS, and seawater given by the proposed PD, visually represented in red, green, and blue, respectively. A random forest (RF) algorithm, developed as part of the AI OBSERVER framework, accurately detected the central OS regions in both datasets, as shown in (c) and (d). Given the print screen in Appendix, showcase the results of the AI-OBSERVE platform for an OS.

The comparative analysis highlights that both the classical approach and the RF algorithm achieve balanced performance in standard scenarios. However, the proposed descriptor exhibits a significant advantage in classifying complex or mixed OS regions, which are often misclassified by other traditional methods. In the future steps, we will deploy ML/DL techniques to classify multiple OS types using other sensors [20].

IV. CONCLUSION

Marine OS pollution poses a significant global environmental challenge, causing long-term damage to marine ecosystems and adversely affecting coastal communities. SAR is a widely used remote sensing tool for OS monitoring. However, most existing studies rely on manual visual interpretation of SAR imagery, which, while practical, is time-intensive and subject to human error. To address this limitation, we utilized dual-polarization SAR data to extract PDs to enhance OS features. Through a series of experiments, we demonstrated that

Fig. 5: (a), and (b) classification of OS by proposed descriptor; (c), and (d) OS discrimination using RF algorithm developed by AI OBSERVER.

the proposed combination of PDs is effective in accurately detecting and classifying OS. Furthermore, the results were benchmarked against an RF algorithm developed by AI-OBSERVER. The findings indicate that both the classical PD-based approach and the RF model achieve comparable performance in central OS detection, with a balanced accuracy across different OS types. This methodology can reliably distinguish among three OS classes: thick OS, thin OS, and oil-free regions.

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APPENDIX

AI-OBSERVER Platform using RF for OS detection.